

Ovicidal activity of insecticides on the rice caseworm *Nymphula depunctalis*

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Eggs of the rice caseworm *Nymphula depunctalis* are laid on the undersides of leaves in contact with the water surface. Because the caseworm is a pest before the rice canopy closes, a significant amount of insecticide applied as a foliar spray reaches the water surface. Granular insecticides broadcast on paddy water would also allow chemical contact with eggs.

We tested the effect of sprayable and granular insecticides as ovicides on the rice caseworm in the field and in an open-air headhouse at IRRI. In the field trial, 1-day-old eggs on cut leaves were placed on the water surface of plots (2 m²) with rice plants 15 days after transplanting. Nine insecticides were sprayed at 0.75 kg a.i./ha in 300liters water/ha. Eggs were moved to the headhouse 48 hours later and placed in petri dishes with water from the treatments. In the greenhouse, 9 sprayable insecticides were applied at 400 ppm to petri dishes with water and eggs of 2 ages (1 and 3 days old) on cut leaves. The 1-day-old eggs were exposed to the insecticide for 24 hours, rinsed, and placed in distilled water until they hatched. The 3-day-old eggs (black-head stage) were also exposed for 24 hours (they hatched on the 4th day). Eggs of 3 ages (1, 2, and 3 days old) were exposed for 24 hours to 3 granular insecticides in basins of water in the headhouse. The granular insecticides were applied at 0.75 kg a.i./ha (375 ppm). All eggs, except those 3 days old, were removed after 24 hours, rinsed, and placed in distilled water until hatching. In the field trial, which represented a natural situation, mortality was 90% on 1-day-old eggs with azinphos-ethyl after 24 hours of exposure (Table 1). Diazinon, triazophos, and malathion were also highly ovicidal. The trial with sprayables in the headhouse produced higher mortalities because the insecticide concentration was higher in the water than in the field. All insecticides, except phosphamidon, were highly effective ovicides. Sprayable insecticides differed in ovicidal activity with egg development. Diazinon and carbophenothion were highly effective on 1-day-old eggs; MTMC was more effective on 3-day-old eggs. All three granular insecticides were highly ovicidal (Table 2). Carbofuran was highly effective regardless of egg age. Diazinon was more active on 1-and 2-day-old eggs, whereas-BHC caused the highest mortality to 3-day-old eggs. The trials included organochlorine, organophosphorus, and carbamate insecticides but no class of insecticides appeared more ovicidal than another.

Table 1. Activity of insecticide sprays as ovicides against rice case worm.

IRRI, 1980. ^{a/}			
Insecticide ^{b/}	Mortality of eggs exposed for 24 h at ^{c/}		
	1 day old		3 days old
	Field ^{d/}	Headhouse ^{e/}	Headhouse ^{e/}
Azinphos-ethyl 40 EC	90 a		
Diazinon 20 EC	78 ab	95 a	20 cd
Triazophos 40 EC	68 abc	94 a	99 a
Malathion 57 EC	44 abc	84a	99 a
BPMC 50 WP	33 bc	96 a	91 ab
Phosphamidon 50 EC	31 bc	19b	12 d
Carbaryl 85 WP	26 bc		
Endosulfan 35 EC	29 bc		
MTMC 50 WP	21 c	41 b	99 a
MIPC 50 WP	12 c	91 a	76 b
Carbophenothion 40 EC		98 a	41 c
Ethion 40 EC		96 a	71 b
^{a/} 100 eggs/replication. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level.			
^{b/} 400 ppm. EC = emulsifiable concentrate, WP = wettable powder.			
^{c/} Mortalities converted using Abbott's formula.			
^{d/} Applied at 0.75 kg a.i./ha on water surface. Av, 2 replications			
^{e/} Av, 3 replications			

Table 2. Activity of insecticides, applied as paddy water granules, as ovicides against rice case worm. IRRI greenhouse, 1980. a/

Insecticide b/	Mortality (%) of eggs exposed for 24 h at ^{c/}		
	1 day old	2 days old	3 days old
Carbofuran 3G	100 a	100 a	97 a
Diazinon 6G	96 a	99 a	82 b
gamma BHC 6G	52 b	31 b	85 b
^{a/} Av, 3 replications (100 eggs/replication). In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level.			
^{b/} Applied at 0.75 kg a.i./ha (375 ppm). G = granular.			
^{c/} Mortalities converted using Abbott's formula			